

“Changing the Screenplay”—Transnational and Feminist Rewritings of Myth in Dubravka Ugrešić’s BABA YAGA LAID AN EGG

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It’s not by accident that the pristine wilderness of our planet disappears as the understanding of our own inner wild natures fades. It is not so difficult to comprehend why old forests and old women are viewed as not very important resources. It is not such a mystery. It is not so coincidental that wolves and coyotes, bears and wildish women have similar reputations. They all share related instinctual archetypes, and as such, both are erroneously reputed to be ingracious, wholly and innately dangerous, and ravenous.

Clarissa Pinkola Estés (1992: 1)

Abstract

This article examines the feminist rewriting of both popular and ancient myth, folk and fairy tales in the works of Dubravka Ugrešić, in particular in her patchwork novel *BABA YAGA LAID AN EGG* (*BABA JAGA JE SNIJELA JAJE*), 2009. By examining the archetype of the evil witch Baba Yaga, which is prominent in folk tales across the Slavic realm, I investigate how Ugrešić uses humor, surprise, and solidarity as narrative strategies to subvert conventional notions of gender, power, family ties, beauty and ageing. Changing the script for fairy tale motifs such as romance and heroism, Ugrešić draws on theoretical thinkers on myth and fairy tales such as Vladimir Propp and Roland Barthes to reflect critically on expectations aimed at women in post-socialist societies and beyond.¹

Keywords: women, archetypes, fairy tales, folk tales, ageing, witches, feminism, heritage

In her best-selling book, *WOMEN WHO RUN WITH THE WOLVES* (1992), the author and Jungian analyst Clarissa Pinkola Estés presented a collection of stories which celebrated ‘the wild woman’ archetype: women from folk and fairy

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tales who undergo hardship, defy social norms, transform into animals or become their companions and ultimately emerge from their trials empowered and wizened. By focusing on female heroines in a genre which was still predominantly occupied by men, Pinkola Estés reframed myth as a tool for feminine self-exploration, as she elaborated in her introduction: “The instruction found in story [sic!] reassures us that the path has not run out, but still leads women deeper, and more deeply still, into their own knowing. The tracks we all are following are those of the wild and innate instinctual Self.” Published at a time when feminist scholarship on fairytales, which had been exploring the subject for two decades, had reached a new peak, Pinkola Estés’ book became a best-seller precisely because it familiarized a wider audience with a new approach to a deeply gendered literary genre.

The rewriting of myths, both ancient and modern, in order to challenge conventional notions of gender, home, and history, and to empower women specifically, has also been a major undertaking in the work of Dubravka Ugrešić. Like Roland Barthes’ approach in his *MYTHOLOGIES*, which explores the modern implementation (and manipulation) of myth, Ugrešić’s work examines the use of popular myths in daily life to present a distorted vision of historical and political facts (a process which Barthes called a “dressing up of reality” and “ideological abuse”; 1991: 10) to further the uneven power dynamics of the status quo. Her analysis of myth, like Barthes’, traces its transmission via seemingly banal and fleeting displays of intangible heritage: the use of myth in public events such as a politician’s speech, nationalist celebrations after a football match, religious and political rituals, newspaper articles or television broadcasts, as well as the idealization of patriarchal icons such as war criminals. And while Barthes was attacking “the general semiology of the bourgeois world” (op. cit.: 10), Ugrešić’s texts aim to expose and undermine the role of the media (both old and new), as well as cultural institutions in promoting sexist social structures in the post-socialist succession states of the former Yugoslavia.

Like Pinkola Estés, who presented herself as a storyteller on the margin and was affirmative of her hybrid identity (being of Mexican-Spanish descent but raised by Hungarian American parents in Michigan (Pinkola Estés 1992: 3)), Ugrešić defies uniform labels about her identity and her literary work. Born in the former Yugoslavia to a Bulgarian mother and a Croatian father, she was one of the first women authors in the socialist republic to enjoy widescale success as a writer, while also teaching at Zagreb’s Institute for Literary Theory. After her anti-nationalist sentiments during the Yugoslav civil war of the 1990s lead to prolonged public harassment, she left the newly independent Croatia, eventually settling in Amsterdam in 1993. Both Pinkola Estés and Ugrešić display a

transnational and nomadic sensibility, which is not least affirmed by the plurilingualism in their writing: the English prose of *WOLVES* is interspersed with expressions in Spanish, while phrases in English, Russian, French and Latin appear in the Croatian original of Ugrešić's *BABA JAGA JE SNIJELA JAJE* (2007; *BABA YAGA LAID AN EGG*, 2009), which explores the Slavic myth of the evil witch Baba Yaga in a contemporary setting.²

Ugrešić approaches myth from the perspective of the marginalized, the underdog—the narrator of her texts is most frequently a female, aging migrant writer of ambiguous nationality and political affiliation, who often encounters other exterritorials and misfits who defy expectations and categorizations. Her writing is both a practice in the spirit of feminist solidarity as articulated by bell hooks, and a transnational decentering of literary circulation. Ugrešić's works, while written in Croatian, appear first in Dutch (Boesch 2007) before being published in the original, but with Serbian publishing houses, then in German, French and English translation. By placing women, migrants and other marginalized characters at the center stage of her modern myths, Ugrešić adds new interpretative layers beyond conventional readings of myth, thus reinvigorating and perpetuating the mythological material itself. One element which is imperative for her decentralizing approach is the use of humor, employing the subversive power of the comic to expose and destabilize dynamics of systemic oppression.³ Furthermore, there is a subtle pedagogical trajectory underlying her writing, marked by rhetorical questions, an investigation of knowledge and its failed transmission, but also by humorously exposing the confusion, vulnerability and uncertainty of both the author-narrator and her protagonists. This self-critical, non-sovereign, hesitant approach to educating the reader has been called "stammering pedagogy" by Sneja Gunew (2017: 25).

Ugrešić first became known as a playful-ironic commentator on social typologies and norms. Her satirical debut novel *STEFFIE SPECK IN THE JAWS OF LIFE* (1992; *ŠTEFICA CVEK U RALJAMA ŽIVOTA*, 1981), followed the adventures of an unhappy Zagreb typist looking for love, combining elements from romance novels, beauty magazines, and women's advice columns and was successfully adapted to an extremely popular Yugoslav film in 1984 by the director Rajko Grlić. Her protagonist is a single typist living with her elderly aunt,

² Unfortunately, the plurilingualism of the book is only partially conveyed in the joint English translation of the book by Ellen-Elias Bursać, Celia Hawkesworth and Mark Thompson.

³ I have written elsewhere about the use of the comic, and its advantages over a purely tragic employment of what Homi Bhabha has called the "minoritarian" experience. See "Laughing in the Face of Adversity. Comedy and Tragedy as Affective Strategies in the Work of Mely Kiyak", in: *Oxford German Studies* Vol. 49 (2020): 174-190.

but the friends she turns to for advice (at the beginning of the novel, Štefica diagnoses herself with depression)—are married ‘emancipated’ women, successful working women, and female intellectuals. Her next book, the experimental, postmodern detective novel *FORDING THE STREAM OF CONSCIOUSNESS* (1991; *FORSIRANJE ROMANA RIJEKE*, 1981) about a literary congress in Socialist era Zagreb again focused on human types, for which she was the first woman author in Yugoslavia to be awarded the prestigious NIN award.

In her playful postmodern novels, Ugrešić was drawing on an autonomous, non-referential understanding of literature that was not geared towards political engagement. The acceptance of formalist literary approaches, in which the autonomy of the artwork was affirmed, had been a strategic decision in the cultural politics of the Socialist state since the late 1960s to deepen the alliance with intellectuals (Lukić 2006: 245). Unlike other authors who had declared themselves feminists early on, Ugrešić did not consider herself a member of any activist group, despite occasionally attending meetings of feminist collectives in Zagreb (cf. Lorand 2018: 110). The Institute for Literary Theory, where Ugrešić taught for decades, was strongly influenced by Russian formalism and French structuralism (cf. Williams 2013: 40-41). Despite the fact that her satirical novels debunked gender myths and problematized social structures, they were not tailored to any particular cause, which changed radically in the 1990s. When Ugrešić criticized nationalist tendencies during the Yugoslav wars, she faced fierce opposition and went into voluntary exile in 1993, after experiencing repeated attacks for her anti-nationalist and anti-war sentiments in Croatia. At the same time when the question of commitment became crucial for her literary work, she shifted her writing from the novel form to the essay, best exemplified in her book *THE CULTURE OF LIES. ANTIPOLITICAL ESSAYS* (1995; *KULTURA LAŽI. ANTIPOLITIČKI ESEJI*, 1994), which addresses issues of memory manipulation during the Yugoslav civil war through a series of essayistic miniatures. Ever since, her publications have included a barely concealed autobiographical narrator: a female writer who has left the former Yugoslavia due to public harassment and nationalist hysteria, and rebuilds her erstwhile home in her mind by gathering anecdotes, news reports, private and collective memories. Ugrešić, who resides in Amsterdam and refuses to be identified as a Croatian writer, has always defied conventional identity politics: in short biographies or on book covers (especially in translated editions) she appears as a European writer who was born in Yugoslavia.

Already in *ŠTEFICA CVEK*, Ugrešić uses a postmodern aesthetic including satire and irony, metaliterary comments and language games to deconstruct female stereotypes and to present the reader with more empowering and modernized feminine archetypes. Like Barthes, Ugrešić resists popular views of myths

“[not] as statements of particular actors, but as outgrowths of nature [...] seen as providing a natural reason, rather than an explanation or a motivated statement”, and as “‘innocent’ speech—from which ideology and signification are absent [...]” (Robinson 2011) Her incorporation of both popular and ancient myth questions not just the stories women have been told about gender, love, and life, but also reclaims their interpretation. Štefica Cvek herself embodies both the exposition and deconstruction of popular myths. The heroine sets out to find happiness (and cure her depression) by finding true love. Following fairy-tale numerological convention,⁴ she has to endure three suitors until she finds ‘the one’ in an English language class. The reader is eventually offered, in post-modern, deconstructive fashion, several possible endings (all happy), leading to the couple’s eventual union. Quite fittingly, Štefica’s somewhat naïve but also endearing adventures are comically juxtaposed to the lamentations of a neurotic male friend grieving over a lost ‘mythical past’. Myth is not rejected as narrative material as such, it is merely stripped of its patriarchal pathos and reframed accordingly. By pointing to the constructedness of feminine myth and offering both the reader and the protagonist the opportunity to tailor their own myths through metaliterary commentary in the form of sewing instructions, Ugrešić offers readers a different experience of femininity (Korljan and Škvorc 2009: 70). The playful approach to myth demonstrated in this early novel assumes a melancholy tone in Ugrešić’s writing on the aftermath of the Yugoslav war in *THE MUSEUM OF UNCONDITIONAL SURRENDER* (1998). In loosely connected essayistic vignettes that depict the narrator-author’s reflections on exile, memory, nostalgia and loss, we also find a gathering of five Yugoslav female friends from different ethnic backgrounds who are visited by an angel and given a feather each, which initiates profound changes in their lives (Ugrešić 1998: 167-192). This theme of female kinship, magical occurrences and birds is continued in the most extensive rewriting of myth in Ugrešić’s work, her book *BABA YAGA LAID AN EGG* (2007), a patchwork novel weaving various components of the Slavic myth of the evil witch Baba Yaga together with the archetype of the wise but also irreverent crone, as well as critical reflections on ageing, community, and social expectations towards women in post-socialist society. Before I delve into a deeper analysis of the novel, I will provide a brief summary of feminist scholarship on folk and fairy tales to allow for a better contextualization of Ugrešić’s book.

⁴ The number three is popular in Grimm’s fairy tales in particular, but has symbolic function in various mythologies (Greek, Christian, Slavic) as well.

Feminist debate since the 1970s had seen critics divided on whether fairy and folk tales could be used to support the feminist cause. In her 1970 essay, "Fairy-Tale Liberation", the anthropologist Alice Lurie had affirmed the feminist potential of folk tales and fairytales which depicted female characters that were resourceful, wise and powerful. Contrary to feminist critics who insisted that the popular transmission of fairytales (i.e., through animated Walt Disney movies) perpetuated gender inequality by making women internalize disempowering myths, Lurie did not consider the characters and tropes in the original fairytales themselves as problematic, but argued that they only became so through their sexist appropriation, distorted transmission and biased selection in a patriarchal society (cf. Haase 2000). Lurie had particularly pointed to lesser-known collections of fairy tales, which were marginalized because they did not lend themselves to promoting the standard narrative of submissive femininity. Similarly, the feminist literary scholar Carolyn G. Heilbrun proposed in 1979 that "myth, tale, and tragedy must be transformed by bold acts of reinterpretation in order to enter the experience of the emerging female self" (Haase 2000: 19). Heilbrun offered the Grimms' fairy tales as an example of cultural texts whose models of male selfhood could be adopted and reinterpreted by women in light of their own search for role models, which proved that fairy tales could serve as crucial "tools of socialization" (Haase 2000: 20). Like Pinkola Estés twenty years later, Lurie emphasized the feminist lessons that could be gleaned from less well-known, marginal folk and fairy tales that may offer gender paradigms different from Grimms' fairy tales and their popular adaptations and have not been subject to as much sexist editing. The structure of *WOLVES* illustrates to what extent the selection and ordering of tales aids a feminist reading. While Pinkola Estés does examine some well-known fairy tales such as Grimms' *BLUEBEARD*, *WOLVES* begins with the Mexican folk tale of *LA LOBA* (Wolf Woman), about a mysterious old woman who is both wise and frightening in her animal-like appearance, "circum-spect, often hairy, always fat [...] both a crower and a cackler" (Pinkola Estés 1992: 19). She avoids company and, similarly to old crones in "fairytales in Eastern Europe", is waiting for the sincere seeker to find her. Meeting her is not for the faint-hearted, for her "sole work is the collecting of bones" [...] and "preserving that which is in danger of being lost to the world". She sings over wolf bones until they grow flesh and the creature, "la criatura" comes back to life and runs away, finally transforming into a laughing woman (Pinkola Estés 1992: 19). The magic *LA LOBA* performs is a reminder of the fragmentation and alienation women are subjected to in a world which does not honor their wholeness: "We all begin as a bundle of bones lost somewhere in the desert. [...] It is our work to recover the parts" (Pinkola Estés 1992: 19). By placing the lonesome crone

archetype as the embodiment of the “Wild Woman” at the beginning of her female-centered collection, Pinkola Estés challenges Western fairytale standards of female happiness, which typically require youth, beauty and partnership of some kind. Ugrešić pursues a similar goal in *BABA YAGA*, unearthing an unconventional and complex role model for feminine empowerment which has been relegated to the realm of shadows in the western tradition.

The book contains three related narrative blocks, themselves filled with essayistic miniatures: the first part relates the author-narrator’s visit to her elderly, dying mother in Zagreb; the second follows three ageing Croatian women, Beba, Kukla and Pupa, on a trip to a Czech spa town; and the third part contains an anthropological compendium or dictionary of Baba Yaga, written by the Bulgarian folklore scholar Aba Bagay, who also appears as an admirer of the author and friend of her ageing mother in part I. Curiously, the compendium is placed at the end of the book instead of its beginning, thus inviting readers to explore their own associations with the myth before giving them the key to understanding specific motifs and symbols. It explains:

Baba Yaga lives in a forest, or on the edge of a forest, in a cramped little hut that stands on hen’s legs and turns around on the spot. She has one skeleton-leg (‘Baba Yaga, bony leg!’), dangling breasts that she dumps on the stove or hangs over a pole, a long sharp nose that knocks against the ceiling [...] and she flies around in a mortar, rowing herself through the air with a pestle, wiping away her traces with a broom.⁵

Baba Jaga živi u gustoj šumi, ili na samom rubu šume, u maloj tijesnoj izbi koja stoji na kokošnjim nogama i okreće se oko sebe. Ona ima jednu nogu koštanu (*Baba Jaga koštjanaja noga*), grudi koje joj vise (tako da ih drži na peći ili ih vješa preko motke), dug, šiljat nos na kojim upire o strop, i leti u stupi pomažući se tučkom i zamećući tragove metlom.⁶

Like many mythical women, Baba Yaga is related to the animal world, specifically birds: “Some cite her as ‘the mistress of all the birds’ (hence the hut on hen legs and the long nose like a beak)” (BYE: 248); “jedni kažu (da je gospodarica ptica’ (od čega joj je preostala izba na kokošnjim nogama i dugi nos koji podsjeća na kljun)” (BYO: 272).

She is also able to shapeshift at her will: “As a witch, she is believed to have the power of metamorphosis and most often turns herself into a black bird (raven, crow, black hen or magpie.)” (BYE: 251); “Vještice, poput drugih mit-skih bića, posjeduju sposobnost metamorfoze [...]. Najčešće se pretvara u crnu pticu (vranu, crnu kokoš, svraku).” (BYO: 274-275) Baba Yaga is ambivalent

⁵ Ugrešić: *Baba Yaga Laid an Egg*. 2009: 247, henceforth BYE.

⁶ Ugrešić: *Baba Jaga je snijela jaje*. 2007: 271, henceforth BYO.

and contradictory: In folktales across different Slavic traditions, she appears both as an evil sorceress who eats children (or drinks their blood), challenges or ruins brave male heroes but also offers guidance and help to those who pass her tests. Like any myth, her story is constantly adapted and expanded:

Baba Yaga is a unique oral-textual 'patchwork' of folklore and mythico-ritual traditions (shamanism, totemism, animism, matriarchy) and her status, function and authority change from tale to tale, from one zone of folklore to another, from male storytellers to female. Baba Yaga is a text that is read, studied, told, adapted, interpreted and reinterpreted differently at different times. (BYE: 248)

Baba Jaga je jedinstven oralno-tekstualan patchwork sastavljen iz raznovrsnih folklornih i mitološko-ritualnih tradicija (šamanizma, totemizma, animizma, matrijarhata), pa se njezin status, funkcija i ovlasti mijenjaju od bajke do bajke, od jedne folklorne zone do druge, od pripovjedača do pripovjedačice. Baba Jaga je tekst koji je u raznim vremenima različito čitan, učitan, prepričavan, adaptiran, readaptiran, interpretiran i reinterpetiran. (BYO: 271-272)

By letting various characters in the book embody the archetype of Baba Yaga in unexpected ways, not just the ageing protagonists of part II, but also the narrator and her mother in part I, as well as the young anthropologist Aba Bagay (an easily recognizable anagram of Baba Yaga) who writes a compendium on 'Babayagology' in part III, Ugrešić modernizes and rewrites the persona of the evil witch most common in western fairytales.

The main objective of the book is challenging conventional perceptions of ageing by making ageing women the protagonists of a modern fairy tale, and also imbuing them with a voice of their own (Gramshammer-Hohl 2021: 357). The theme of the first part is the invisibility and silencing of older women. The author-narrator's mother is losing her speech through cancer metastases in her brain (which she calls 'paučina' or cobwebs in the original) that result in partial amnesia and mixed-up words. On the one hand, the moments of verbal confusion reveal both the narrator's and her mother's grief and shame over the unavoidable physical decline that come with illness and aging. On the other, Ugrešić uses these moments to demonstrate the older woman's stubborn defiance of death, often to great comic effect: for example, when her mother cannot remember the name for "cereal/cerealije" cookies, she asks to be brought "genital cookies/kekse za genitalije" instead (the English translation pairs the more modest "congested" with "digestive" cookies). Language confusion later gives way to language reduction, when the mother begins repeating the same pieces of quotidian wisdom that provide her with a sense of familiarity and safety:

Onions should always be well sauteed. Good health is what matters most. Liars are the worst people. Old age is a terrible calamity. Cleanliness is half of health. Always discard the first water when you cook kale. (BYE: 18)

Luk se uvijek mora dobro izdinstati. Najvažnije je zdravlje. Lažovi su najgori ljudi. Starost je velika nesreća. Grah je najbolji na salatu. Čistoća je pola zdravlja. Kad kuhaš kelj, uvijek baci prvu vodu. (BYO: 30)

These phrases resemble the beauty, health and household advice that Ugrešić inserted in *ŠTEFICA CVEK* to illustrate the discourse of femininity that young women in 1980s Yugoslavia were subjected to, only now the ageing mother appears as the compressed archive of these popular beliefs. Having accepted the dominant societal narrative that "old age is a terrible calamity", the narrator's mother tries to defy age and stave off death by wearing bright colors, putting away portraits of the deceased, and refusing to board black taxis. At the same time, a counter-image to this narrative is established through the mother's oldest and closest friend, the retired gynecologist Pupa, whom she calls "the old witch". Unlike the mother, Pupa is frustrated by her own longevity. Nearly immobile and half blind, she insists on living by herself in her Zagreb apartment, terrorizing a rotating cast of cleaners and accusing her daughter, with whom she is in perpetual conflict, of not letting her die. In her acerbic wit and difficult demeanor, but also in her curious appearance, Pupa appears as the personification of the mythical Baba Yaga:

She'd sit in an armchair with her feet tucked into the big fur boot, sniffing the air. [...] With her closely cropped hair, a birdish, beak-like nose, she'd elegantly curve her neck and direct her grey gaze at the visitor. (BYE: 20)

Sjedila bi u fotelji s nogama uvučenima u golemu čizmu, njuškajući zrak oko sebe [...] kratko ošišane sijede kose, oštra, povijena nosa nalik na kljun, elegantno bi povijala svoj dugi vrat i upravljala svoj sivi pogled u posjetiočevu pravcu. (BYO: 32)

As the dictionary in part III clarifies, Pupa's one-legged and bird-like exterior evokes depictions of Baba Yaga's travels in a mortar, and her transformations into birds. Pupa is placed at the center of a web of female protagonists in *BABA YAGA* who are connected through various tales circulated throughout the book. One of them is the "family legend" ("obiteljska legenda", BYO: 31) about the narrator's birth, which ties her fate to Pupa's: As the assistant gynecologist at the narrator's birth, Pupa pranked her mother into believing that her newborn daughter was ugly ("Lord, what a hideous child, Pupa said when they pulled you out. My heart sank with fright." BYE: 19; "Isuse, kakvo ružno dijete!, – rekla je Pupa kad su te izvukli van. Premrla sam od straha.", BYO: 31). The narrator's life thus begins with a joke that simultaneously affirms the

close bond between Pupa and the narrator's mother, but also offers a display of 'the old witch's' power. Significantly, the mother relates the interaction with the 'old witch' to convey fondness and pride, thus subverting the insulting and frightening connotations of the label 'witch' that have been carried over into the (post)modern era. It is important to note that Pupa embodies several qualities assigned to women who were defamed as witches throughout history: For one, her medical profession places her amongst the many midwives, herbalists, and other healers persecuted for their knowledge around the human body and childbirth (cf. Huttun 2017). While she was successful as a gynecologist, however, her tumultuous life has continuously placed her in the role of misfit and troublemaker.

Born as Pupa Singer to a Jewish family in Zagreb, she experiences a life full of hardship. As the narrator laments: "The wind blows, then calms down, but Pupa's troubles last her whole life." (BYE: 201; "Vjetar puše, pa se smiri, a Pupina muka trajala je cio njezin život.", BYO: 225). Pupa joins the Partisan resistance after the fascist ally Independent State of Croatia declares its own racial laws in 1941, but her first husband dies fighting in the Second World War, and she is forced to send their young child to London to be taken in by with her paternal grandparents. In Socialist Yugoslavia, Pupa is first celebrated as a Partisan heroine, but then thrown into the anti-Stalinist labor camp Goli Otok, which prevents her from travelling abroad and reuniting with her estranged daughter for over two decades. Her second marriage to a Serb raises suspicion in the neo-nationalist environment of the 1990s, and she finds herself in perpetual conflict with her second daughter, also a gynecologist, who turns into a fervent Croatian patriot. Just like Baba Yaga, Pupa is a misfit, as she refuses to adapt herself to the changing tides of history and finds herself isolated from both family and national community. As the dictionary elaborates:

In modern terms, Baba Yaga is a 'dissident', beyond the pale, isolated, a spinster, an old fright, a loser. She never married, and apparently has no friends. If she had any lovers, their names are not known. She does not care for children, she is no devoted mother, nor—despite her advanced years—has she become a granny surrounded by beloved grandchildren. She is not even a good cook. Her function is at once crucial and marginal: 'courteous' or 'rude' heroes stop when they reach her hut, they eat, they drink, they steam in her bath, take her advice, accept magical gifts that help them to reach their goals and then disappear. They never come back with a bunch of flowers and a box of chocolates. (BYE: 313)

Prevedeno na nešto moderniji jezik, Baba Jaga je 'disidentkinja', izopćenica, usamljenica, 'stara cura', stara rugoba, gubitnica. Nikada se nije udavala, i čini se, nema prijatelja. Imena njezinih ljubavnika, ako ih je imala, ostaju nepoznata. Ne voli djecu, nije brižna majka, nit je, unatoč poznim godinama, postala baka okružena voljenim unucima. Nije čak ni dobra kuharica. Njena funkcija

je istodobno ključna i marginalna: 'ljubazni' ili 'neljubazni' junaci zaustave se pred njezinom kolibom, najedu se, napiju, popare u njezinoj banji, okoriste se njezinim savjetom, prime čarobne darove koji će im pomoći da dođu do cilja, i iščeznu. Nijedan od njih nije se vratio buketom cvijeća i kutijom čokoladnih bombona i ponovno zakucio na njena vrata. (BYO: 334)

Baba Yaga also fulfills the function of the female scapegoat, the one upon whom all projections of a thoroughly self-alienated society can be directed:

Baba Yaga is a surrogate-woman, she is here to get old instead of us, to be punished instead of us. Hers is the drama of old age, hers the story of excommunication, forced expulsion, invisibility, brutal marginalization. On this point, our own fear acts like acid, which dissolves actual human drama into grotesque clownishness. Clownishness, it is true, does not necessarily have a negative overtone: on the contrary, in principle it affirms human vitality and the momentary victory over death! (BYE: 314)

Baba Jaga je surogat-žena, ona je tu da stari umjesto nas, da bude stara umjesto nas. Njezina drama je drama starosti; njezina je priča priča o izopćeništvu, o prisilnom otpadništvu, o nevidljivosti, o brutalnoj marginalizaciji. Pritom naš vlastiti strah djeluje poput kiseline, koja stvarnu ljudsku dramu rastvara u groteskno komedijašenje. Komedijašenje, istina, nema nužno negativan prizvuk: naprotiv, ono u načelu afirmira ljudsku vitalnost i trenutnu pobjedu nad srmću! (BYO: 334-335)

The elements of humor and playfulness (or "clownishness," as stated above) are part of the subversive, defiant strategy of the text and are implemented through comical interactions in part II of *BABA YAGA*. This middle section narrates the spa holiday which the octogenarian Pupa undertakes with her two younger friends, Kukla and Beba, who are in their 70s. Pupa refuses to act the part of the sweet old lady, repeatedly insulting male characters who try to lecture her on aging and mortality. She expresses her boredom unabashedly by simply falling asleep. Her friend Beba, on the other hand, like the narrator's mother in part I, mixes up words when she gets excited, wishing the hotel guests, for example, "a nice lay" instead of "a nice day", or rattles off numbers when under distress which lead to lottery wins. Part II is also spattered with cheerful rhymes that are reminiscent of children's fairytales but also offer playful metaliterary commentary:

What about us? We carry on. We wish Pupa, Kukla and Beba pleasant dreams, while we hasten to reinforce our stories' seams. (BYE: 100)

A mi? Mi idemo dalje. Zaželimo miran san Pupi, Kukli i Bebi, a mi ćemo ostati budni, da priča nam pobjegla ne bi. (BYO: 116)

But, as life is lived slowly and tales are told swiftly, we're going to fast forward a bit here, and we'll slow things down later [...]. (BYE: 101)

Ali kako se život živi sporo, a priča se priča hitro, mi ćemo ovdje malko zabrzati naprijed, a kasnije malko usporiti [...]. (BYO: 117)

Yes, the three old girls had missed learning a lot more, but we too, unfortunately, must press on. While people yearn for what they cannot get, the tale hastens on, with no regret! (BYE: 114)

Da tri stare djevojke propustile su da saznaju još mnogo štošta, a i mi, nažalost, moramo dalje. Dok čovjek za propuštenim obično žali, priča se na drugi način kali – i niš' joj ne fali! (BYO: 131-32)

The tale, as the narrator makes clear, has its own dynamic and agenda, even if its pace can be adjusted when needed. At the end of the spa episode, much-yearned for death finally comes for Pupa, and her body is flown into Zagreb in a giant painted egg that Beba and Kukla have acquired at a Russian specialty shop (BYE: 231). Beba and Kukla, too, find their happy endings not just through the unexpected bout of fortune which is Pupa's inheritance, but also through caring for Beba's adopted Chinese granddaughter Wawa (Beba's estranged gay son Filip, dying of Aids, had tasked a friend with finding his mother and putting the child into her care), who appears miraculously just after Pupa passes away, thus creating a new all-female family unit. As aging, barren, single caretakers, and allies of a publicly ostracized woman, they form a new trio which subverts the official role that Ugrešić has seen allotted to women in the post-Socialist period with the resurgence of nationalist ideology:

With the fall of Communism, the position of women in the post-Communist societies deteriorated from its earlier status. The Communist image of the independent woman who'd been part of the workforce (in post-World War II propaganda this was a priority because the workforce faced a shortage of men and needed women!) was replaced by the image of the porn star or the submissive wife who winds herself and her whole life onto three spools: children, church, kitchen. The resurgence of nationalist ideology in post-Communist countries has had a major impact on the instrumentalization of women. (Ugrešić 2016: 39).

In this vision, there is no place for voices of dissent or women who do not contribute to the building of the new homogenous nation. What is left to the misfits, then, is "intervening in the screenplay" (BYE: 221), as the protagonist Beba calls it in discussion with Arnos Kozany, one of the spa guests at the Grand Hotel. This intervention can only happen through a reconfiguration of the text—in life as in myth, this becomes a reassertion of female creative agency. Imagining the future of their foster child Wawa, the two remaining witches

Beba and Kukla therefore endow her with the bold combination of both fairytale wonder and narrative-linguistic mastery:

Life was an endless garden filled with hidden Easter eggs. Some people collected basketfuls, others did not find a single one. Perhaps that's what they ought to teach Wawa—how to be a hunter, a hunter of wonders. Not to miss anything, to enjoy every second, for life is the only thing we are given free of charge. (BYE: 233)

Život je kao nepregledan vrt, prepun skrivenih uskršnjih jaja. Netko sakupi punu košaru, netko ne pronade nijedno. Možda tomu treba naučiti Wawu, kako da bude lovac, lovac na čuda. Da ne propušta, da uživa u svakoj sekundi, jer samo nam je život dat besplatno. (BYO: 258)

Given that the heroines take centerstage in *BABA YAGA*, what happens to the male characters in this feminist fairytale? As a scholar of Russian formalism and modern prose, Ugrešić was keenly familiar with Vladimir Propp's *MORPHOLOGY OF THE FOLKTALE* (1928), in which various narrative functions of dramatis personae, situations and motivations typical for the Russian *volshbenaya skazka* are analyzed, and Propp is also mentioned several times in the *Baba Yaga* dictionary at the end.⁷ In his book, Propp describes narrative patterns such as a hero departing for a journey, being given a task, being tested by a villain or marrying as the final reward. Not only are the heroic roles typically reserved for men in folk and fairy tales filled by women in Ugrešić's book, but Propp's typology is disrupted in several ways. In part I, the narrator-author goes to Bulgaria for a literature conference, but imagines herself as a "bedel", an Ottoman substitute soldier or pilgrim, sent on a mission by her mother (who grew up in Varna) to revisit and photograph sites from her mother's childhood and seek out erstwhile friends. While both the hero's departure and the solving of an important task (a quest) are mentioned by Propp as fairy tale tropes, Ugrešić's major intervention is that the narrator is not given this quest, but invents it herself because she believes that photographs of Varna will give her mother joy and help jog her ailing memory. Furthermore, the role of the "bedel" in the Islamic context is exclusively male, since women do not go on isolated quests such as the *hajj*. The narrator does not succeed, however, in performing her assigned task, since she is denied access to locations of her mother's youth such as her former school and the house in which she was raised.

⁷ See for example, "Vladimir Propp argues that the myths of many tribal cultures contain two worlds: the world of the living and the world of the dead" (BYE: 258), and "Vladimir Propp explains *Baba Yaga*'s masculine attributes as a travesty (disguising a man as an old woman) of tribal rituals for the transition from matriarchy to patriarchy." (BYE: 273)

She also feels disrupted in her quest by the young Bulgarian folklore scholar Aba Bagay, who imposes her company on the author. Pretentious, insecure as well as emotionally and financially needy, Aba appears as the obstacle to the “bedel’s” task or as a fairy tale villain. She does, in fact, assume characteristics of Baba Yaga, who has a habit of testing heroes. Like Pupa, Aba is described as having bird-like features, “Živahne tamne oči, malko povijen nos i ti nesretni okviri davali su njezinu licu ptičji izraz” (BYO: 55). Curiously, this exact sentence, which could be rendered as “Her lively dark eyes, slightly hooked nose and those unsightly glasses gave her face a bird-like appearance”, is missing in the English translation of the same paragraph (BYE: 44).

She also embodies the shapeshifting, timeless qualities of the old witch, which is confirmed in the dictionary as well. When Aba complains about hair loss, and the author observes that this only happens to older women, she declares herself both an infant and an old woman:

‘I am an ageing woman’—‘You are just a baby still.’—‘Babies are ageing women.’ (BYE: 57)

‘Ja sam stara žena.’—‘Ti si još beba.’—‘Bebe su stare žene’. (BYO: 70)

This is also a clever pun pointing to the ironic name of 70-year-old Beba in the second part of the book, with “beba” (literally meaning baby, but also doll) being a frequent female nickname in the former Yugoslavia. In the Baba Yaga dictionary in part III, we are told that Kukla and Pupa’s names (which are also nicknames, the original names are never disclosed) also point to puppets and dolls (BYE: 288; BYO: 308). The dolls evoked here are not the little girls’ toys which promote patriarchal ideals of beauty and feminine care, however, but rather magical objects of ancient tribal traditions and matriarchal animism—the “doll as the abode of ancestral spirits (the mother’s, in this case)” [...] (BYE: 286); “Lutka je stanište predaka, ovdje majke [...]”, BYO: 307). They signify fertility, protection and power: “Dolls which possess protective powers are hereditary: mothers bequeath them to their daughters.” (BYE: 287; “Lutke koje imaju zaštitnu moć nasljeđuju se: majka takvu lutku ostavlja svojoj kćeri.”, BYO: 308). The three heroines of part II, but also the folklore scholar Aba are therefore placed in a lineage of sorceresses who defy categorizations of age and femininity. They are not toys to be played with, but instead consciously or unconsciously enchant and manipulate the men around them, who underestimate them due to their age. Most importantly, their main pursuit is not a male companion but female kinship.

Propp observed that the hero’s quest usually ends with a marriage, but the question of romantic love is toppled from its conventional fairy tale pedestal by Ugrešić. When the narrator asks Aba the expected question whether she has

a boyfriend, Aba replies with a Russian fairytale instead of giving a straightforward answer (BYO: 72-73). In the fairy tale, the hero Ivan has to cross seven hills, seven valleys, seven seas and retrieve a magical egg to feed to his beloved princess in order to regain her love. He manages to make her eat the egg, but only by deceit, and Aba ends her story without relating the triumphant reunion of the lovers. In real life, it is implied, relationships are more complicated than in fairy tales, and not worth the labor and trouble (again, this interpretation is confirmed later in the dictionary which also serves as an interpretative handbook for the narratives in part I and II). Significantly, all the women in Baba Yaga are single. The men who try to come to their rescue (usually with their own hidden agenda) are systematically exposed as lacking hero potential or humbled towards a more pragmatic, modest masculinity.

When the three older women arrive at the Czech spa hotel, the arrogant receptionist Pavel Zuna feels a strange pain in his left foot and then faints. Shortly after, they are approached by Mr. Shake, an American charlatan and crook, who built his "kingdom" by peddling useless supplements and powders that promise youthfulness but paradoxically lead to impotence: "His products suggested to frogs that they would turn into princesses." (BYE: 92), "Njegovi proizvodi sugerirali su žabama da će se pretvoriti u princeze." (BYO: 107) He is presented as the disseminator of the modern-day fairytale of endless magical transformation:

Mr. Shake activated the acupuncture point of the archetypal dream that slumbers in each of us, a dream in which, with the aid of a magic potion, the dreamer can become as small as a poppy seed, pass through any keyhole, become invisible, be transformed into a giant, vanquish a terrible dragon, and win the heart of the beautiful princess." (BYE: 92)

Mr. Shake aktivirao je akupunktursku točku arhetipskog sna koji drijema u svakome od nas, sna u kojemu se sanjac uz pomoć čarobnog napitka može smanjiti na veličinu makova zrna, provući kroz svaku ključanicu, postati nevidljiv, pretvoriti se u džina, savladati strašnoga zmaja i zadobiti srce prekrasne princeze." (BYO: 107-8)

In the postmodern age of disenchantment, the only "territory" left for magical transformation is the human body (BYO: 108), the ultimate feat being the prevention or reversal of the aging process. The fact that Mr. Shake is quite unceremoniously excised from the story through a fatal golf ball misfired by Kukla can be read as darkly humorous commentary on the questionable merit of these beliefs.

A similar critique of the ideology of youthfulness is demonstrated through the character of Dr. Topolanek, the head of the hotel's wellness center and the son of disillusioned former Czech dissidents, who made a career for himself

through reckless opportunism, and is now selling age-defying wellness treatments to rich foreign tourists. When he first approaches the trio to invite them to his talk on longevity, he is affronted by Pupa who exclaims: “Crap! Prolonging old age indeed! It’s youth you want to prolong, not old age!” (BYE: 99); “Drek! Kakvo produžavanje starosti! Produžite mladost, a ne starost!” (BYO: 115) Even though he is taken aback by this harsh rebuttal and the old woman’s general rudeness, Topolanek attempts to win the trio over by taking a feminist stand during his presentation on longevity: He explains that biblical mythology has only honored the longevity of men (such as Methusalem, Adam, Enos, and Seth) because it was written by men (“... things are quite different in mythology. There it is exclusively the men who are long-lived, which makes sense since the creators of that mythology were men.” (BYE: 111); “... u mitologiji stvari stoje posve drukčije. Tamo su dugovječni isključivo muškarci, logično, kreatori mitologije bili su muškarci.” (BYO: 128)), whereas the future belongs to women. Men, he claims, will soon be discarded onto the “rubbish heap of history” (BYE: 111; “smetlište historije”, BYO: 128) because advancements in reproductive medicine will mean that they will no longer be needed for reproductive purposes. The three witches, however, are merely bored by Topolanek’s advances and leave his talk early.

The character that comes closest to a stereotypical ‘prince charming’ from Disney’s fairytale adaptations but is also humorously deconstructed in that function is the young and handsome Bosnian masseur Mevludin, who offers exotic foam massages at the hotel spa, for which he assumes the costume and persona of an Ottoman Turk, Sulejman. Beba meets Mevludin when she is encouraged by Kukla and Pupa to take some time to pamper herself in the spa and is both confused and enticed when she notices that her supposedly Turkish masseur is sporting a permanent erection. When she discloses her origins, they bond over their mutual Yugoslav heritage and Mevludin reveals that his state of arousal is a “curse” brought upon by a Serbian grenade during the Yugoslav civil war, making him the object of unsolicited desire and commodification, thus ruining both his mental health and his relationships (BYO: 124-125). Because of his beauty, Pupa compares Mevludin to Apollo, but he freely admits his stupidity (“I’m a fool, love”; BYE: 109; “Ja sam ti bona, blento”; BYO: 125) and does not even know who the mythical figure is. In the dictionary we learn that Mevludin is modeled after the archetype of the male ‘fool’, a clueless hero who is underestimated by everyone and achieves success by bravery, not by wits, such as “Ivan the Fool” in Russian fairy tales. This archetype, however, could never be transferred to a heroine:

Allow me to mention here that the stupid girl, one who spends all day picking her nose and lazing on the stove, and eventually becomes a princess or a queen,

is completely unthinkable in fairytales! [...] Wealth, a throne, and love are only conceivable for grubby, idle, stupid guys! (BYE: 285)

Napominjem ovdje da je glupa djevojka, koja po cio dan kopa nos i valja se na peći, i na kraju postaje princezom ili kraljevnom – posve nezamisliva u bajkama! [...] Bogatstvo, prijestolje i ljubav zamislivi su kao nagrada samo – prljavom, lijenom, glupom mladiću! (BYO: 307)

But because Mevludin is not merely foolish, but also possesses a good heart, a fact that he asserts himself ("My soul is as soft as a Bosnian plum"; BYE: 176; "Duša mi je meka ko bosanska šljiva"; BYO: 199) and that is confirmed by the three witches, he is eventually rewarded with love.

Seeking the witches' advice to win the heart of Rosie, the overweight daughter of Mr. Shake, Mevludin asks them to describe the ideal man so that he can model himself after his traits. He approaches Pupa first, who reminds him of a sacred hen ("svetu kokoš"; BYO: 194) about to lift her wing and is thus recognized as the embodiment of Baba Yaga. Pupa declares that her perfect man is Superman, because of his ability to fly and his protective powers such as a see-through gaze, from which she conducts that "[H]e's a handyman, someone who fixes everything around the house" (BYE: 173); "Majstor, taj ko ima zlatne ruke i sve popravlja po kući" (BYO: 196). But more importantly, he also "mends the world" ("[on] je popravljajac svijeta", BYO: 196) by fighting evil. Beba says that her ideal man is Tarzan, because he is "half-ape, half-Lord" (BYE: 175), "pola majmum, pola lord" (BYO: 198), referring to the literary character John Clayton II in the TARZAN book series by Edgar Rice Burroughs, also known as Lord Greystoke, who is of noble English descent, but is raised by an ape tribe in the African jungle after his parents die. Kukla offers the wisest answer, saying that her favorite man is the devil, since "the devil is a man with a long, powerful and convincing history of seduction [...] the only opponent of God himself, who is, as we know, also a man." (BYE: 176); "Đavo je muškarac s dugom, moćnom i uvjerljivom zavodničkom biografijom. Đavo je jedini suparnik samo Bogu, koji je, kao što znamo, također muškarac" (BYO: 199). Dejected, Mevludin concludes that he cannot embody any of the characters since he does not know how to save the world, lacks the airs of a lord, and is too good-hearted to be the devil. This humorous competition around ideal masculinity mirrors traditional male notions of an ideal woman or wife, with both Pupa and Beba highlighting gender stereotypes about men being practical with their hands and engaged in worldly affairs, while also being allowed to simultaneously embody both wildness and sophistication. At the same time, it also critiques the extent to which supernatural fairytale standards

have also disempowered men in the postmodern age, who will never be able to fulfill them.

Mevludin breaks the mold by defying both ancient and modern fairytale archetypes with his kindness and authenticity: he finally reenacts the fairytale mentioned earlier in the book with Rosie, handing her a boiled egg with the words “here’s my heart on a silver platter” (BYE: 164, same in the original). The girl takes a bite, then shares the egg with Mevludin, which makes their mutual love blossom, and Mevludin’s cursed erection disappears: “Just as the wretched shell had cast a spell on him, this girl with the egg in her hand had broken it” (BYE: 165). “Kako ga je ona nesretna granata bila začarala, tako ga je ova djevojka s jajetom u ruci očarala” (BYO: 186). The egg here is a symbol for the transformative power of Baba Yaga, which is taken to hyperbolic heights at the end of part II: When Pupa dozes off and dies in the pool while the women are celebrating an unexpected lottery win for Beba, her dead body is even more reminiscent of a bird, with claws revealed in lieu of toe nails, and “her knees bent and slightly parted like an oven-ready Christmas Turkey” (BYE: 180; “sa savijenim i malko raširenim koljenima poput onih orijaških američkih thanksgiving-purica, pripremljenih za pećnicu”, BYO: 203). As it later turns out, Pupa has turned herself into the celebratory turkey for her friends by leaving them a substantial sum of money, her “golden eggs.” Even in death, she remains true to herself: As her twisted limbs and her rigid bent hand with two raised fingers (presumably a victory sign) will not fit into a child’s coffin, Beba and Pupa purchase a giant painted egg in the spa town, in which the remains are eventually transported back to Zagreb, together with her signature fur boot. The death that Pupa has longed for comes across as a planned gift and offering for Beba and Kukla, who can now start a new abundant life with Beba’s adopted granddaughter Wawa, as a non-traditional, matriarchal family unit (Xue 2014: 151).

In *BABA YAGA*, Ugrešić challenges the values, messages and archetypes of popular fairytales by confronting the reader with a fairytale archetype that is too complex for modern consumption and transcends representations of the witch and the wise woman in Western fairytales. Instead of depicting Baba Yaga as the frightful, grotesque old witch who awaits her victims and truth seekers in a forest hut, she imbues contemporary ageing heroines with her symbolism and quality, thus making them visible in a social context that wants to discard them. Baba Yaga becomes a symbol of feminine empowerment through her irreverence, wisdom, her skills of transformation and reinvention, her crude humor and stubbornness. By defying common expectations directed at women such as youth, beauty, family planning, good health, meekness and

compliance, the heroines of Ugrešić's book are able to find fulfillment in themselves, and create a meaningful life through a feminist community of care.

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